

EDUCATIONAL LEADERSHIP EFFECTIVENESS: IS IT A MATTER OF A LEADER'S CHARACTERISTICS, BEHAVIORS, OR LEADERSHIP STYLE? A CORRESPONDENCE ARTICLE

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ABSTRACT

This review explores educational leadership effectiveness. Educational leadership has been well studied up to this point, with particular attention paid to the most prevalent leadership models, the traits and qualities of charismatic leaders, and the main conduct and style of leadership. However, to the best of our current understanding, more research on the effectiveness of educational leadership concerning these characteristics needs to be done. This review paper also aims to investigate links and associations between the traits, actions, leadership philosophies, and efficacy of leaders. The literature review indicates that there is no definitive answer to the question of which of the actions, personal traits, and leadership styles contribute more to effective leadership. Studies have indicated that each of these components is essential and deemed significant for the efficacy of education. Additionally, it is asserted that they are intricately linked as discrete components of a larger system, each of which has a varying degree of influence on the efficacy of educational leadership. In addition to reviewing the research on the characteristics and outcomes of leadership techniques that are effective in enhancing student learning, this paper offers a quick review of key ideas that are essential to understanding educational leadership.

Keywords: *education, leadership, management, efficiency, effectiveness, styles, characteristics*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching school administrators includes teaching them about leadership, which is a crucial topic for any inexperienced principal, in addition to program design. According to Jerdborg (2020), there is a rising knowledge that being a principal requires specific training. This

realization stems from the realization that leadership is crucial to the success of schools and that school leadership has become more difficult. Studies on school leadership education indicate that the course material should be pertinent to the learners; that is, learning-oriented leadership, organizational growth, and change management should be prioritized, along with the integration of theory and practice.

School administrators are professionals who establish partnerships and collaborate with diverse groups to achieve positive outcomes through the establishment and accomplishment of transformative goals. They are practitioners who work in applied jobs, even though many of them have postgraduate degrees and can work in academic contexts. Educational leaders approach problem-solving comprehensively, relationally, and with evidence by tying theory to practical initiatives and circumstances. The idea of leadership has occasionally been interpreted and analysed based on the personality traits of the leader, their actions, the outcome they achieve, and their style of command, or using "hybrid" models that incorporate the theories (Pruitt, 2023).

For this assessment, leadership is defined as exerting influence on various stakeholders and members of the organization to identify and accomplish the goals and vision of the school. This influence is typically employed through relationships between and among individuals, groups, and the surroundings in which they find themselves. It is typically reciprocal rather than unidirectional and originates from several sources (e.g., administrators, parents, teachers, trustees). According to this definition, a leader is considered "successful" when they contribute to the organization's vision and goals in a significant, positive, and ethically sound way (Jerdborg, 2020).

For this reason, leadership can emerge from a variety of places—administrators of schools and districts, educators, parents, members of school boards, and representatives of the state government, for instance. While leadership from various sources can impact the enhancement of student learning, this review primarily focuses on the leadership exhibited by school and district administrators, teachers, and other educators, as their influence is greater than that of other sources.

Education leaders set the tone for their organizations' principles. They inspire instructors and staff to give their all in addition to motivating pupils. Through cooperation, commitment, and communication, they foster success.

Effective leadership is the result of a blend of managerial abilities and professional knowledge used in every phase of school administration, from systemization to planning to execution (Brooke, 2017).

Those in charge of education must also design the systems that influence the workplace and classroom. Research indicates that there is a relationship between student learning outcomes, professional development, and school leadership. Education leaders establish standards for the procedures and output of the school.

Research Questions

The general research question that this study attempts to address is whether the effectiveness of educational leadership results from some unique traits that set successful educators apart, or whether the effectiveness of leadership is a byproduct of behaviors or suitable leadership philosophies will try to address these three fundamental research concerns by citing the findings of other pertinent studies based on the body of literature.

Research question 1: Are the results of the educational leadership that is implemented influenced by the personal characteristics of the leaders and what are these specific characteristics?

Research question 2: Are the results of educational leadership influenced by the leadership exercised style and behaviors and which are the main styles?

Research question 3: Which is the most significant component among characteristics, styles, and behaviors of leadership effectiveness?

METHODOLOGY

This Correspondence Article Concentrates on Educational Leadership Effectiveness Results Searching for publications named "Educational Leadership" using Google Scholar is the first step in the review process. Looks are restricted to papers published between 2018-2023. There were 150 articles on this theme once they were identified. The study's articles met the following criteria:

1. Findings from a qualitative study on school instructional leadership strategies
2. Asian study (carried out within the nation of Asia)
3. English must be used to write the article.
4. Theses and dissertations are not accepted.

The following are the steps included in the Educational Leadership:

Step 1: Identify the issue.

- Pick an area of interest and a topic that suits the problem.
- The problem needs to be accurately and fully written.

Step 2: Locate the Reference Materials

- Seek out pertinent readings.
- Learn the main points of the research topic.
- When a research source is backed by subject-matter expertise, it can be highly beneficial.

An overview or synopsis of the earlier study is given by these sources.

Step 3: Assess the Information

- Examine any additions made to the subject matter.
 - Look for and locate the appropriate data source as needed to bolster the study,
 - Information must be qualitative.
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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The community of educators, researchers, parents, students, and education, in general, are becoming more and more concerned with the topic of educational leadership effectiveness, and many studies have been conducted to determine how it affects the various parties involved.

The goal of this review was to add to the understanding and debate surrounding the elements, traits, and leadership styles of school leadership as well as its effectiveness. Within the framework of a study of the literature on educational leadership, the correlation and interaction of these components with one another were highlighted. Furthermore, traits associated with the successful application of leadership in the sphere of educational units were documented, reported, and linked to the different styles and efficaciousness of leadership.

Research question 1: Are the results of the educational leadership that is implemented influenced by the personal characteristics of the leaders and what are these specific characteristics?

Regarding the research questions, and particularly the first one, it is clear from the quotation of pertinent literature that a leader's qualities do, in fact, directly or indirectly affect the

outcome of their leadership exercise because these qualities enable, contribute to, shape, and influence their leadership style, which in turn affects the outcome itself (Dimopoulos,2020).

The author characterizes these leaders' approach to the reform initiatives as directed by their fervent convictions in democratic and collaborative procedures. Additionally, it is very important to influence the leadership style so that will be able to give a great outcome.

Research question 2: Are the results of educational leadership influenced by the leadership exercised style and behaviours and which are the main styles?

In response to the second research question, it is recognized and understood through the citation of pertinent literature that applied leadership style and behaviour do have a direct effect. This is because each of the briefly mentioned styles functions differently for the recipients, contributes, shapes, and influences team member performance to varying degrees, and ultimately, as we have seen, each leadership style assigns weight to distinct goals.

According to the author, these findings are consistent with the findings of another study that showed a strong correlation between leadership styles and academic performance (Dimopoulos,2020).

Research question 3: Which is the most significant component among characteristics, styles, and behaviors of leadership effectiveness?

Regarding the third study issue, it is known and supported by the citation of pertinent literature that it is impossible to determine the most important element among the traits, actions, and styles of effective leadership accurately and objectively. In terms of the idea of educational leadership effectiveness, significant findings have been made about how to define it in principle as well as how to gauge and evaluate leadership effectiveness using particular standards and parameters (Dimopoulos,2020).

The author claims that when assessing the effectiveness of educational leadership, one can interpret criticism and evaluate a leadership style, but it cannot be objectively measured based on the traits of the leader using it; that is, based on whether or not the leader possesses some or all of the traits listed in this study. Additionally, the leadership style used by the leader can be used to interpret the effectiveness of educational leadership, but it cannot be objectively measured. Specifically, the application of the style that the leader chooses to use each time is examined, determining what was ultimately achieved and to what extent their respective objectives were pursued. An amalgamation of leadership traits, styles, and corresponding behaviours.

Conclusions

It is crucial to comprehend how educational leadership affects a wide range of stakeholders, including instructors, staff members, and students. A better understanding of the effects of educational leadership through its fundamental elements, as well as how and to what extent each influences the operation of the educational administration and its outcomes and which element is more significant, can lead to a better understanding of what an educational leader should do to improve their competencies, identify their weaknesses and work to strengthen them, modify their style of leadership, or adopt a different behavior that is more appropriate for the situation at hand. Ultimately, realizing how important leadership elements are to day-to-day operations and combining them successfully can empower leaders to take action.

A primary driving force for the review's completion was the provision of data that would aid in the development of a more explicit focus on equity in the context of effective leadership in behavior, characteristics, and leadership style. The findings show that practically every

leadership activity in the framework may be implemented in a way that promotes fair circumstances and/or results for students.

According to these findings, school administrators have the power to modify how fairly children are treated at their institutions in practically every aspect of their work, not simply by implementing particular policies or attitudes.

The practice of collaboratively combining the skills and energies of educators, learners, and parents is known as educational leadership. Improving the standard of instruction as well as the educational system as a whole is the aim of educational leadership. See why educational leadership is becoming more and more crucial by reading on.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This paper has a single author and confirms that the author reviewed this study

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REFERENCES

- Brooke, E. (2017), Four Key Factors of Effective School Leadership. Retrieved from
Dimopoulos, A. (2020), Educational Leadership Effectiveness. Is it a Matter of a Leader's Characteristics, Behaviors, or Leadership Style?
Jerdborg, S.(2020), Educating School Leaders: Engaging in Diverse Orientations to Leadership Practice. Retrieved from
Pruitt, K. (2023), What Is Educational Leadership and Why It's Important